

Smart Hygiene Monitoring In Cloud Kitchen Using MobileNetv2

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Abstract— Cloud kitchens no longer have a physical space for diners to sit and eat. They depend only on online orders. Manual hygiene monitoring in a large cloud kitchen is a tough venture. Right here a smart real-time hygiene monitoring system detects whether or not the kitchen employees are preserving hygiene or not. To train the version OpenCV is used. To broaden the version MobileNetv2 is used. The actual-time hygiene tracking system facilitates putting off the requirement of manual tracking that is regularly inaccurate and time-eating even as making groups' day-by-day operations green and danger-loose. The MobileNetV2 model yielded an accuracy score of 0.99 and an F1 score of 0.99 in the training data.

Keywords—cloud kitchen, MobileNetv2 model for object detection, real-time hygiene monitoring in cloud kitchen

I. INTRODUCTION

One cannot overstate the significance of hygiene in a meals-related commercial enterprise. Maintaining proper hygiene is a social and ethical obligation as flawed hygiene may affect the fitness of the workers and the customers adversely. Additionally, lack of hygiene can speedily tarnish the photo of the cloud kitchen in query and it may come to be dropping business. It is also essential that the people who're in direct contact with the food keep proper non-public hygiene as properly. Most meal-borne illnesses unfold due to a loss of hygiene consciousness. This system detects whether the man or woman on the camera is following hygiene protocols or no longer.

If the employees aren't following hygiene protocol then the system sends an alert. The system makes use of a Mobile Netv2 model for hygiene detection using Python, Keras, and OpenCV. Those kinds of systems could be very supportive for lots sorts of eating places around the world.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Christa et. al. [1] have created a mask identification system based on convolutional neural networks with OpenCV and MobileNetV2. Using MobileNetV2, they were able to effectively develop a model using CNN architecture that produced an excellent outcome with perfect detection accuracy.

Galvez et. al. [2] have shown that CNN's two cutting-edge models are capable of object identification. They demonstrate that compared to Faster-RCNN with InceptionV2, which has lower speed but higher accuracy, the SSD with MobileNetV1 has high-speed detection but poor accuracy.

Chandan et. al. [3] have suggested utilising deep learning and OpenCV to create a real-time object tracking and detection system. The SSD algorithm detects objects in real time with a high degree of certainty.

Bappy et. al. [4] They demonstrate how a CNN may be utilised to propose regions by activating the receptive fields in their object detection studies. This method creates semantically significant and object-related regions.

Kodali et. al. [5] To make the technique as accurate as feasible, a simple Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model was developed utilising TensorFlow, Keras, Scikit-learn, and OpenCV. In order to access the webcam for real-time face mask detection, Javascript API is helpful.

III. MOTIVATION

In reality, consistent with the meals safety and standards Authority of India, these lately issued hints that meal enterprise operators need to observe to keep their restaurants open in the course of this pandemic. This extraordinary time has compelled eating place companies to ensure the maximum amount of hygiene and disinfection to maintain their enterprise practices. Besides preserving the kitchen smooth, it is also crucial that the employees who're in direct touch with the food keep proper personal hygiene as properly. Manual hygiene monitoring in a large cloud kitchen is a totally hard project. This paper presents a way for computerized hygiene tracking in actual time.

IV. PROPOSED WORK

1. Hardware

A webcam has been used as the hardware component in this paper.

1.1 Web Camera

A web camera is a video camera that is connected to a computer and feeds video in real-time to a computer network. Webcams are typically tiny cameras that are either built into a PC's hardware or connected externally via USB cords. Users using webcam software can take pictures, record videos, or stream the videos online. This proposed model has been put to the test in real time using a web camera with full high-definition (FHD, 1080p) vision specifications.

2. Software Component

The code for this paper has been executed in PyCharm IDE.

2.1 PyCharm

A Python-specific Integrated Development Environment (IDE), PyCharm offers a wide range of crucial tools for Python developers. These tools are tightly integrated to produce a practical environment for effective Python, web, and data science development.

3. Methodology

In this study, we present the MobileNet CNN convolutional neural network architecture, a very efficient feature extractor for object recognition. The supplied dataset is used to train the neural network in order to construct a model for identifying hygienic and unclean individuals in the image. The trained classifier will determine whether or not the subject is sanitary. Preprocessing has been done using OpenCV. Figure 1 depicts the methodology's workflow diagrammatically.

Figure 1: Workflow of the hygiene monitoring system

3.1 Dataset

The dataset used for the paper is a set of hygiene protocol images. The dataset contains about 1006 equally distributed images of 2 distinct types. Two types are images of people with facemasks and images of people without a face masks.

3.2. Pre-Processing

There was a lot of noise and duplication in the training dataset. The model's accuracy is dependent on the chosen training dataset. Therefore the dataset must be preprocessed before being input. According to the MobileNetV2 model, the photos are scaled and their pixel representation is transformed into a list format. A NumPy array is then created from this list to facilitate rapid mathematical computations.

3.3. Data augmentation

Large amounts of data are required to train the MobileNet V2 model in order to avoid under fitting and hasten the convergence of the neural network model. The data augmentation strategy has been employed to make up for the little dataset because there wasn't enough data to train the model. Numerous variations of the same image were produced during this procedure by rotating, zooming, shifting, shearing, and flipping each image.

3.4. OPENCV-CNN

An open-source package called OpenCV is designed to carry out computer vision tasks. It has been used to get rid

of for pattern recognition, features with the removed feature can be backpropagated.

3.4.1 Convolution layer

A feature map is created from the convolutional layer's output. The convolution filter with width and height, the sum of input and output channels, the convolution filter depth, and convolution operations are the characteristics that CNN uses.

3.4.2 ReLU Layer

Deep learning models frequently employ the activation function known as the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU). It is a method of supervised learning. If the input is positive, the output of a ReLU function follows it; otherwise, the output is zero.

3.4.3 Pooling Layer

The area of features in the input has an impact on the feature map that is produced. This sensitivity can be exceeded, and the feature map necessitates a feature down sampling. This increases the speed at which the generated feature maps to changes in the aspect in the image's bearings. By adding up the existence of aspects in the feature map, pooling procedures can be used to speed up calculations while reducing the dimensions of the input matrix with the exception of any aspect loss.

3.4.4. Fully-Connected Layer

The model is expanded to include the fully linked layers, which are fully connected to the activation layers. All of the inputs in this layer are linked to the activation component of the layer below. The provided photos are multiclassified, and the activation function is applied in layers to get the predicted output classes' probabilities.

3.5. MobileNetV2

A convolutional neural network of 53 layers deep is called MobileNet-v2. Because of the simplified and smaller models, MobileNetV2 models run more quickly. These deep learning models are regarded as excellent mobile deep learning models due to their compact size. A trained model for picture classification is called MobilenetV2. Deep neural networks that have been trained using a sizable image dataset are called pre-trained models. MobileNetV2 is a deep neural network that has been used to the categorization issue. Pre-trained models avoid wasting computational resources. It will group people into those who maintain good hygiene and those who don't.

V. RESULT

The results of this experiment are carried out using a laptop and PyCharm for the development and implementation process. The datasets are separated by labeling with hygienic and without hygienic. These folders are loaded along with their pixel values to train the model. The images are pre-processed and converted into NumPy arrays for faster calculation. For classification models, Keras has been used. The training datasets are 70% and the remaining 30% is for testing purposes. After 20 epochs, the average accuracy of the mobilenetv2 model turns out to be 99%. Calculation of Accuracy and Precision was measured for positive predicted values. The classifier's ability was determined by Recall. The measure of the test accuracy plot was given by F1 score. The training accuracy plot is shown in figure 2.

Figure 3. A kitchen employee spotted with a mask

Figure. 2. Training Loss and Accuracy curve

TABLE I

Dataset	Classification Report		
	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Without Mask	1.00	0.99	0.99
With Mask	0.99	1.00	0.99

Table.I.Performance metrics obtained

TABLE II

S.No	Comparison of Accuracy and F1 score for different architectures.			
	Architecture Used	Year	Accuracy	F1-Score
1	LeNet – 5	1998	84.6	0.85
2	AlexNet	2012	89.2	0.88
3	ResNet – 50	2016	92.7	0.91
4	CNN (Proposed model)	2021	99	0.99

Table.2. Comparison chart of different algorithms

VI. CONCLUSION

This research presents a MobileNetV2 model-based approach for monitoring hygiene in cloud kitchens. The Mobilenet model's second version is referred to as MobilenetV2. The parameter count of the deep neural network is significantly lower. Deep neural networks as a result get lighter. Tensorflow and Keras can be used to train the model. Data classification functions are incorporated into Keras. The process of data augmentation comes next, and once it is complete, the model is ready to be tested using actual data.

The work has great future scope, as this kind of model will be integrated with CCTV or different kinds of cameras to stumble on and perceive humans without the right hygiene.

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